

Research on Mobile Advertising Users' Propagation Ability Evaluation based on the Neutrosophic Cubic Number Multiple-Attribute Decision-Making

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Abstract: The evaluation of mobile advertising users' propagation ability assesses how effectively users can share or spread advertisements within their networks. It involves analyzing factors such as user engagement, social influence, sharing frequency, and network reach. By understanding these metrics, advertisers can identify highly influential users who can amplify campaign impact. This process helps optimize targeting strategies, improve ad performance, and maximize return on investment by leveraging users with strong propagation potential in mobile advertising ecosystems. The mobile advertising users' propagation ability evaluation is multiple-attribute decision-making (MADM). In recent years, the MOORA approach has been widely utilized to address multi-attribute decision-making (MADM) problems. To handle the uncertainty inherent in such problems, neutrosophic cubic sets (NCSs) have emerged as a powerful tool for expressing and analyzing uncertain information. This research introduces a novel approach, the neutrosophic cubic number MOORA (NCN-MOORA) approach, to solve MADM problems under the framework of NCSs. Specifically, the approach is applied to evaluate the propagation ability of mobile advertising users, a critical factor in optimizing advertising strategies. To demonstrate the validity of the proposed approach, a numerical case study is conducted. The primary objectives of this research are as follows: (1) to propose the NCN-MOORA approach for solving MADM problems within the NCS environment; (2) to determine attribute weight information using average method, ensuring an unbiased weighting process; (3) to design and apply the NCN-MOORA approach for evaluating mobile advertising users' propagation ability and compare its performance with existing approaches; and (4) to validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach through comparative analysis. The results confirm that the NCN-MOORA approach offers a reliable and efficient solution for evaluating mobile advertising users' propagation ability in uncertain environments.

Keywords: Multiple-attribute decision-making (MADM); Neutrosophic cubic sets (NCSs); MOORA approach; Mobile advertising users' propagation ability evaluation.

1. Introduction

Mobile advertising users' propagation ability refers to their capacity to share and disseminate advertising content within their networks, thereby amplifying the reach and impact of marketing campaigns. In the mobile advertising ecosystem, users act as key drivers of content distribution, influencing how effectively promotional messages spread through social platforms and digital communities. Propagation ability is crucial because it determines the extent to which advertisements can engage a larger audience through user interactions. This ability is influenced by various factors, including the user's level of activity, their influence within their network, and the size and quality of their connections. Users with strong propagation abilities often act as "key influencers," capable of encouraging others to engage with and further share the content. As mobile platforms continue to dominate the advertising landscape, understanding and leveraging user propagation ability has become a strategic priority for marketers. Evaluating propagation ability allows advertisers to identify high-value users who can maximize the visibility of their campaigns. By targeting these users, businesses can achieve better engagement rates, reduced costs, and improved conversion outcomes. Moreover, the dynamic and unpredictable nature of mobile advertising environments makes propagation ability a critical metric, as it ensures that campaigns stay relevant and effective in competitive markets. The earliest research focused on the technological applications of mobile advertising. In 2008, the partnership between mInfo and Nokia introduced a mobile advertising model centered on lifestyle information searches. By providing Nokia users with integrated search services, this study pioneered technological innovation in mobile advertising[1]. In 2012, Facebook launched a strategy to embed advertisements into users' news feeds through "sponsored stories," leveraging social data to increase ad revenue. However, this approach faced challenges due to users' resistance [2]. Also in 2012, Xiao and Wu [3] constructed a theoretical model for mobile ad adoption based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). They found that factors such as entertainment, credibility, and informativeness significantly influenced users' willingness to adopt mobile ads. Later, Xiao [4] proposed a user attitude model, demonstrating that interactivity is a critical factor in shaping user attitudes, with personalization also having a significant positive impact. With the explosive growth of the mobile advertising market, the focus shifted to user experience and innovation. In 2014, Hong and Li [5] explored user-centric innovation models for mobile advertising,

emphasizing that user experience is a key factor for the future development of mobile advertising. By 2016, attention turned to the design and implementation of context-aware advertising. Wang and Zhao [6] proposed a context-aware service attraction model based on user behavior, improving ad relevance and appeal by analyzing the user's current environment and interests. In 2017, research moved toward optimizing the efficiency of mobile ad propagation. Xu and Yang [7] introduced a location-based mobile ad distribution strategy. By studying users' spatiotemporal characteristics and budget constraints, they designed a heuristic algorithm that significantly improved advertising propagation efficiency. Zhu and Wang [8] investigated user attitudes and preferences toward mobile ad visual design, providing targeted principles for ad designers. Finally, in 2021, Li [9] proposed a precision ad-push method based on user profiling and collaborative recommendation. By predicting the rating matrix using RBF neural networks, the method improved recommendation accuracy and user interest estimation. In summary, from early technological implementations to user behavior analysis, and later to precision targeting and propagation optimization, research in mobile advertising has gradually advanced toward user-oriented and intelligent approaches.

The evaluation of mobile advertising users' propagation ability is a MADM problem. Recently, the MOORA approach [14] has been widely applied to address MADM issues. NCSs [15] have emerged as a powerful tool for characterizing uncertain data, making them particularly suitable for evaluating users' propagation ability in mobile advertising. However, existing approaches often fail to address situations where attribute weight information is completely unknown. This motivates us to design a weight determination approach based on average and score values under NCSs. Furthermore, while many decision-making algorithms apply MOORA approaches independently to identify optimal solutions, limited studies have explored integrating these two approaches under the framework of NCSs. To the best of our knowledge, no or very few studies have focused on developing a MOORA approach using weighted averages under NCSs. Therefore, this research proposes a novel NCN-MOORA approach, which integrates the strengths of MOORA while employing an average-based weighting approach. The NCN-MOORA approach is specifically designed to deal with the MADM problems under the uncertain environment of NCSs. This paper dealt with the NCN-MOORA approach and applied it to the evaluation of mobile advertising users' propagation ability. To validate the proposed approach, a numerical case study is conducted. The

study demonstrates the practical applicability and effectiveness of the NCN-MOORA approach in real-world decision-making scenarios.

1.1 Criteria Definitions

Below are 10 criteria to evaluate the propagation ability of mobile advertising users, ranked in order of importance from highest to lowest with full descriptions.

1.1.1 Influence (High Priority)

The extent to which a user can impact others' opinions, behaviors, or purchasing decisions. Users with a high number of followers or connections who actively engage with their content are more influential.

1.1.2. Engagement Rate

The level of interaction a user generates on their posts, such as likes, shares, comments, and clicks. High engagement indicates a strong connection with their audience and greater propagation potential.

1.1.3. Reach

The total number of people a user can potentially reach through their posts or shares. This includes both direct followers and extended networks accessed through shares or reposts.

1.1.4. Content Relevance

How closely does the user's content align with the themes or goals of the advertising campaign. Relevance ensures that the message resonates with the target audience.

1.1.5. Sharing Frequency

The consistency and frequency with which a user shares or interacts with mobile advertisements. Frequent sharing enhances the probability of an ad reaching a wider audience.

1.1.6. Credibility

The trustworthiness of the user as perceived by their audience. Users with a reputation for providing authentic and accurate information are more likely to propagate ads effectively.

1.1.7. Virality Potential

The likelihood of a user's shared content going viral. This is influenced by the user's creativity, timing, and ability to capture trending topics or sentiments.

1.1.8. Social Network Centrality

The user's position within their social network, such as whether they are a hub for information sharing. Central users are better positioned to propagate messages effectively.

1.1.9. Platform Diversity

The number of platforms the user is active. Greater diversity increases the spread of the advertisement across different audience segments.

1.1.10. Demographic Alignment

The similarity between the user's demographic profile and the target audience of the advertisement. Alignment ensures that the propagated message reaches the intended recipients.

The primary contributions of this research are summarized:

- Proposing the NCN-MOORA approach for solving MADM problems under NCSs.
- Determining attribute weight information using an average-based approach.
- Designing and applying the NCN-MOORA approach to evaluate mobile advertising users' propagation ability and comparing it with existing approaches.
- Demonstrating through comparative analysis that the NCN-MOORA approach is both effective and reliable for evaluating mobile advertising users' propagation ability.

The research structure of this paper is outlined: Section 2 introduces the NCSs, which serve as a foundational tool for addressing uncertainty. In Section 3, the NCN-MOORA approach is developed under the framework of NCSs. Section 4 presents an illustrative case study to evaluate the propagation ability of mobile advertising users, along with a comparative analysis to validate the proposed approach. Section 5 provides concluding remarks and insights constructed from the study.

2. Preliminaries

Ail et al. [15] constructed the NCSs based on SVNSSs [16] and IVNSSs[17].

Definition 1 [15]. The NCSs are constructed:

$$A = \left\{ \left(\theta, \left(I_A(\theta), S_A(\theta) \right) \right) \mid \theta \in X \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $I_A(\theta)$ is IVNSs and $S_A(\theta)$ is SVNSs in X . And

$$I_A(\theta) = ([TL_A(\theta), TR_A(\theta)], [IL_A(\theta), IR_A(\theta)], [FL_A(\theta), FR_A(\theta)]) \tag{2}$$

$$S_A(\theta) = (TT_A(\theta), II_A(\theta), FF_A(\theta)) \tag{3}$$

$$[TL_A(\theta), TR_A(\theta)], [IL_A(\theta), IR_A(\theta)], [FL_A(\theta), FR_A(\theta)] \subseteq [0,1] \tag{4}$$

$$TT_A(\theta), II_A(\theta), FF_A(\theta) \in [0,1] \tag{5}$$

$$0 \leq TR_A(\theta) + IR_A(\theta) + FR_A(\theta) \leq 3, \quad 0 \leq TT_A(\theta) + II_A(\theta) + FF_A(\theta) \leq 3 \tag{6}$$

The neutrosophic cubic number (NCN) is constructed:

$$A = \{([TL_A, TR_A], [IL_A, IR_A], [FL_A, FR_A]), (TT_A, II_A, FF_A)\}.$$

Definition 2[15]. Let $A = \{([TL_A, TR_A], [IL_A, IR_A], [FL_A, FR_A]), (TT_A, II_A, FF_A)\}$ and

$B = \{([TL_B, TR_B], [IL_B, IR_B], [FL_B, FR_B]), (TT_B, II_B, FF_B)\}$, the laws of the operation be

constructed:

$$(1) A \oplus B = \left\{ \left(([TL_A + TL_B - TL_A TL_B, TR_A + TR_B - TR_A TR_B], [IL_A IL_B, IR_A IR_B], [FL_A FL_B, FR_A FR_B]), (TT_A + TT_B - TT_A TT_B, II_A II_B, FF_A FF_B) \right) \right\};$$

$$(2) A \otimes B = \left\{ \left(([TL_A TL_B, TR_A TR_B], [IL_A + IL_B - IL_A IL_B, IR_A + IR_B - IR_A IR_B], [FL_A + FL_B - FL_A FL_B, FR_A + FR_B - FR_A FR_B]), (TT_A TT_B, II_A + II_B - II_A II_B, FF_A + FF_B - FF_A FF_B) \right) \right\};$$

$$(3) \lambda A = \left\{ \left(([1 - (1 - TL_A)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - TR_A)^\lambda], [(IL_A)^\lambda, (IR_A)^\lambda], [(FL_A)^\lambda, (FR_A)^\lambda]), (1 - (1 - TT_A)^\lambda, (II_A)^\lambda, (FF_A)^\lambda) \right) \right\}, \lambda > 0;$$

$$(4) (A)^\lambda = \left\{ \left(([(TL_A)^\lambda, (TR_A)^\lambda], [1 - (1 - IL_A)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - IR_A)^\lambda], [1 - (1 - FL_A)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - FR_A)^\lambda]), ((TT_A)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - II_A)^\lambda, 1 - (1 - FF_A)^\lambda) \right) \right\}, \lambda > 0.$$

Definition 3[18]. Let $A = \{([TL_A, TR_A], [IL_A, IR_A], [FL_A, FR_A]), (TT_A, II_A, FF_A)\}$, the score, accuracy, certainty values are constructed:

$$NSV(A) = \frac{(6 + TL_A + TR_A + TT_A - IL_A - IR_A - FL_A - FR_A - II_A - FF_A)}{9} \tag{7}$$

$$NAV(A) = \frac{(TL_A + TR_A + TT_A - IL_A - IR_A - FF_A)}{3} \tag{8}$$

$$NCV(A) = \frac{(TL_A + TR_A + TT_A)}{3} \tag{9}$$

Definition 4[18]. Let $A = \{([TL_A, TR_A], [IL_A, IR_A], [FL_A, FR_A]), (TT_A, II_A, FF_A)\}$ and $B = \{([TL_B, TR_B], [IL_B, IR_B], [FL_B, FR_B]), (TT_B, II_B, FF_B)\}$, Then the comparison laws for NCNs be constructed:

- (1) if $NSV(A) < NSV(B)$, then, $A < B$;
- (2) if $NSV(A) = NSV(B)$, and $NAV(A) < NAV(B)$, we have $A < B$;
- (3) if $NSV(A) = NSV(B)$ and $NAV(A) = NAV(B)$, and $NCV(A) < NCV(B)$, we have $A < B$;
- (4) if $NSV(A) = NSV(B)$ and $NAV(A) = NAV(B)$, and $NCV(A) = NCV(B)$, we have $A = B$.

Definition 5[19]. Let $A = \{([TL_A, TR_A], [IL_A, IR_A], [FL_A, FR_A]), (TT_A, II_A, FF_A)\}$ and $B = \{([TL_B, TR_B], [IL_B, IR_B], [FL_B, FR_B]), (TT_B, II_B, FF_B)\}$, the NCN Euclidean distance (NCNED) and NCN Hamming distance (NCNHD) be constructed:

$$NCNED(A, B) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{9} \left(|TL_A - TL_B|^2 + |TR_A - TR_B|^2 + |IL_A - IL_B|^2 + |IR_A - IR_B|^2 + |FL_A - FL_B|^2 + |FR_A - FR_B|^2 + |TT_A - TT_B|^2 + |II_A - II_B|^2 + |FF_A - FF_B|^2 \right)} \tag{10-a}$$

$$NCNHD(A, B) = \frac{1}{9} \left(|TL_A - TL_B| + |TR_A - TR_B| + |IL_A - IL_B| + |IR_A - IR_B| + |FL_A - FL_B| + |FR_A - FR_B| + |TT_A - TT_B| + |II_A - II_B| + |FF_A - FF_B| \right) \tag{10-b}$$

3. Methodology

This section shows the steps of the NCN-MOORA approach. In 2004, Brauers presented the Multi-Objective Optimization Ratio Analysis (MOORA) method, which is regarded as an objective (non-subjective) approach. Additionally, while ranking options, both desirable and unpleasant criteria are applied simultaneously to choose a higher or better option. There are numerous uses for this approach. The following characteristics of the MOORA approach are present: It falls under the category of compensating techniques. Qualitative qualities are transformed into quantitative attributes; attributes are independent.

Step 1. Create a decision matrix.

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} r_{11} & \cdots & r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{m1} & \cdots & r_{mn} \end{pmatrix}; i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n \quad (11)$$

Step 2. Normalize the decision matrix

We normalize the decision matrix between the criteria and the alternatives.

$$n_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m r_{ij}^2}} \quad (12)$$

Step 3. Determine the reference points.

We compute the reference points for the positive criteria by maximizing the normalized values and the negative criteria by minimizing the normalized values.

Step 4. Compute assessment values.

$$U_j = \sum_{j=1}^g n_{ij} w_j - \sum_{j=g+1}^n n_{ij} w_j \quad (13)$$

Where g refers to the number of positive criteria and n-g refers to the number of negative criteria.

Step 5. Final rank of alternatives.

We ranked alternatives based on the highest value of the assessment values.

4. Results

This section shows the results of the proposed method. The mobile advertising users' propagation ability evaluation is a MADM issue. Eight mobile advertising companies are assessed with 10 attributes.

Step 1. We build the decision matrix using the neutrosophic numbers as shown in Table 1. Then we obtained the score function. Then we combined these values into one matrix. Then we compute the criteria weights by the average method.

$$C1= 0.098935017, C2= 0.0997919, C3= 0.099730694, C4= 0.100176623, C5= 0.100832401, C6= 0.099678232, C7= 0.100342753, C8= 0.099573307, C9= 0.100561346, C10= 0.100377728.$$

Step 2. Then we used Eq. (12) to normalize the decision matrix.

$$n_{11} = \left(\frac{0.51667}{\sqrt{(0.51667 + 0.52481 + 0.53037 + 0.52889 + 0.52111 + 0.50926 + 0.52074 + 0.53889)}} \right) = 0.34866$$

$$n_{12} = \left(\frac{0.52481}{\sqrt{(0.51667 + 0.52481 + 0.53037 + 0.52889 + 0.52111 + 0.50926 + 0.52074 + 0.53889)}} \right) = 0.35416$$

$$n_{13} = \left(\frac{0.53037}{\sqrt{(0.51667 + 0.52481 + 0.53037 + 0.52889 + 0.52111 + 0.50926 + 0.52074 + 0.53889)}} \right) = 0.35791$$

$$n_{14} = \left(\frac{0.52889}{\sqrt{(0.51667 + 0.52481 + 0.53037 + 0.52889 + 0.52111 + 0.50926 + 0.52074 + 0.53889)}} \right) = 0.35691$$

$$n_{15} = \left(\frac{0.52111}{\sqrt{(0.51667 + 0.52481 + 0.53037 + 0.52889 + 0.52111 + 0.50926 + 0.52074 + 0.53889)}} \right) = 0.35166$$

consumers and distributors of content. Propagation ability highlights the extent to which users facilitate the spread of promotional messages, which is influenced by factors such as their social connections, activity levels, and influence within their networks. By identifying users with strong propagation abilities, advertisers can strategically target these individuals to amplify the visibility and effectiveness of their campaigns. One of the key challenges in evaluating propagation ability lies in the inherent uncertainty and complexity of user behavior. Mobile advertising operates in a dynamic environment where factors such as user preferences, engagement levels, and network structures constantly evolve. To address these challenges, advanced decision-making methods are often employed to effectively analyze and evaluate propagation ability while accounting for uncertainties. Techniques such as MADM approaches, including TODIM and VIKOR, are widely used to navigate the complexity of these evaluations. These methods enable a structured assessment of users by considering multiple attributes and identifying the most influential individuals within a network. Another consideration in evaluating propagation ability is the role of data-driven techniques and tools to process and analyze large volumes of information. Mobile platforms generate vast amounts of data, including user interactions, sharing patterns, and network connections. This data serves as the foundation for evaluating propagation ability, enabling marketers to uncover insights into user behavior and identify key influencers within the system. Advanced modeling techniques, such as neutrosophic sets, have been introduced to manage the uncertainty inherent in such data, providing a more comprehensive and accurate evaluation. Ultimately, the evaluation of mobile advertising users' propagation ability serves as a strategic tool for optimizing advertising efforts. By understanding how users disseminate content and identifying those with the greatest influence, advertisers can improve targeting strategies, enhance campaign reach, and maximize engagement. This evaluation process is essential for leveraging the full potential of mobile platforms in modern advertising. The results show alternative 7 is the best and alternative 2 is the worst.

4.2 Comparative analysis

The NCN-MOORA approach is compared with the NC-VIKOR approach [20], NC-Cross Entropy[21], and NCN-GRA approach [22]. The comparative results are constructed in Table 2.

Table 2. Order of different approaches

<i>Methods</i>	<i>Order</i>
<i>NC-VIKOR approach [20]</i>	A7>A3>A6>A5>A4>A8>A1>A2
<i>NC-Cross Entropy[22]</i>	A7>A3>A5>A6>A4>A8>A1>A2
<i>NCN-GRA approach [23]</i>	A7>A3>A4>A6>A5>A8>A1>A2
<i>Our model</i>	A7>A3>A4>A6>A5>A8>A1>A2

From the detailed analysis above, it is evident that all five models lead to the same optimal choice, and the ranking order of these approaches remains consistent. This consistency validates the reasonableness and effectiveness of the proposed NCN-MOORA method. By demonstrating alignment across different models, the reliability of the NCN-MOORA approach is further confirmed, solidifying its utility in addressing MADM problems. Additionally, the proposed NCN-MOORA approach offers a more robust and precise decision-making framework compared to other existing methods. Its ability to handle complex decision environments with uncertain and inconsistent information sets it apart as a superior technique. This method integrates the strengths of both MOORA under the framework of neutrosophic cubic sets (NCSs), making it a versatile and dependable tool for decision-making scenarios.

One of the key features of the NCN-MOORA approach is its consideration of the bounded rationality of decision-makers (DMs). Unlike traditional methods that assume fully rational behavior, the NCN-MOORA approach acknowledges that DMs often operate under constraints such as limited information, time pressures, and cognitive biases. By incorporating this realistic perspective, the proposed method provides results that are better aligned with real-world decision-making processes.

Furthermore, the NCN-MOORA approach effectively minimizes the impact of abnormal or extreme

evaluation values. In MADM problems, outlier values can significantly distort results, leading to unreliable conclusions. The proposed method addresses this challenge by integrating the neutrosophic cubic set framework so that the influence of such abnormal values is reduced. This leads to more balanced and accurate decision outcomes. In conclusion, the NCN-MOORA approach is a powerful and effective approach for solving MADM problems. Its ability to accommodate bounded rationality, mitigate the effects of extreme values, and deliver consistent and reliable results makes it a valuable tool for decision analysis. By surpassing the precision and reliability of other methods, this approach contributes significantly to the advancement of decision-making methodologies in uncertain environments.

4.3 Managerial Implications of This Study

By effectively evaluating mobile advertising users' propagation ability, managers can strategically enhance their advertising impact, foster meaningful user relationships, and drive sustainable brand growth.

1. Identifying High-Value Users

Implication: Managers can pinpoint users with the highest propagation potential, such as influencers or opinion leaders, to amplify advertising reach. Action: Focus resources on collaborating with these high-value users for targeted campaigns to maximize ROI.

2. Optimizing Content Strategy

Implication: Insights into user engagement and sharing behaviors help managers tailor content to align with users' preferences and interests. Action: Create engaging, shareable, and relevant content that resonates with users and motivates them to propagate the message.

3. Enhancing Campaign Targeting

Implication: Propagation ability evaluation allows managers to identify specific demographics and platforms where users have the greatest influence. Action: Allocate advertising budgets to platforms and user segments that offer the highest propagation potential.

4. Improving Engagement Metrics

Implication: Understanding engagement patterns enables managers to refine strategies for fostering deeper connections between users and the brand. Action: Focus on increasing likes, shares, and comments by designing interactive and emotionally resonant campaigns.

5. Encouraging Peer-to-Peer Advocacy

Implication: Users with high propagation ability act as brand advocates, fostering organic growth through peer recommendations. Action: Develop referral programs, gamified sharing incentives, or exclusive offers to encourage users to share content widely.

5. Conclusion

The evaluation of mobile advertising users' propagation ability is essential for understanding how effectively users can spread advertising content within their networks. In the digital advertising ecosystem, users act not only as content consumers but also as distributors, playing a critical role in amplifying the reach and influence of campaigns. Propagation ability reflects a user's capacity to engage with and share advertisements, influencing how well messages are disseminated across social platforms or mobile networks. This evaluation is particularly important as advertisers aim to identify key influencers who can enhance the visibility and impact of their campaigns. By understanding the dynamics of content sharing and user influence, businesses can better target individuals who maximize reach and engagement. However, the evaluation process is complex due

to the uncertainties in user behavior and the dynamic nature of mobile platforms. Advanced decision-making models, such as those incorporating neutrosophic cubic sets, are often used to address these challenges. These methods allow advertisers to account for uncertainty, incomplete data, and behavioral variability, offering a more robust framework for evaluating users' propagation capabilities. Ultimately, assessing propagation ability helps optimize advertising strategies, ensure more effective resource allocation, and improve overall campaign performance. It is a crucial step in leveraging the power of mobile advertising.

The evaluation of mobile advertising users' propagation ability is a MADM problem. This type of evaluation is crucial for understanding how effectively users disseminate advertising content within their networks, which directly impacts the success of advertising campaigns. Recently, the MOORA approach has been widely applied to solve MADM problems due to its ability to handle conflicting criteria and provide a balanced solution. However, in environments with uncertain and incomplete information, conventional methods may struggle to deliver accurate and reliable results. To address this, NCSs have been introduced as a powerful tool for characterizing and managing uncertainty during the evaluation of mobile advertising users' propagation ability. In this manuscript, we propose the NCN-MOORA model, a novel integrated approach designed to solve MADM problems under the framework of NCSs. This model combines the strengths of MOORA while leveraging the flexibility of NCSs to represent uncertain and imprecise information. The NCN-MOORA approach is specifically applied to evaluate mobile advertising users' propagation ability, providing a robust and comprehensive framework for decision analysis in uncertain environments.

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, a numerical case study is conducted.

The case study demonstrates how the NCN-MOORA model performs in real-world scenarios and

highlights its ability to deliver consistent and reliable results. Additionally, a comparative analysis with existing methods is provided to further confirm its practicality and superiority.

The key contributions of this research are summarized:

- The NCN-MOORA model is introduced to address MADM problems under the framework of NCSs, offering a novel approach for handling uncertainty and complexity.
- The NCN-MOORA model is specifically designed for evaluating mobile advertising users' propagation ability and is compared with other existing approaches.
- The comparative analysis reveals that the proposed NCN-MOORA approach is highly effective and reliable for evaluating propagation ability in uncertain environments.

This research provides a valuable contribution to MADM methodologies and offers a practical tool for optimizing mobile advertising strategies.

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